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ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING AS A NEW TECHNICAL FRONTIER IN THE DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION OF RAW EARTH ARCHITECTURE

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Abstract

Earthen construction has a thousand-year history, with evidence of buildings made from this material dated back to different eras and cultures around the world. Consider that the first urban agglomerations built of earth date back to 10.000 years ago in Mesopotamia. Babylon was also built of earth, as well as the famous Tower of Babel, which indicated its center. Since then, this practice has become generalized, spreading to almost every country in the world, so that today at least one third of the world population live in earthen architecture. The earthen material in contemporary times is not considered a valid building material because of bias against its strength and durability over time. Although there is an indisputable variety of earthen construction techniques in the world, two main material use procedures can be distinguished. On the one hand, *pisè de terre*, referring to the traditional construction of walls at least 50 cm thick, made by compressing the earth within lateral formworks that are gradually moved as the work progresses. On the other hand, *adobe*, which uses unfired air-dried earth bricks, after being shaped within special molds, and then used in the traditional way for the construction of walls or in a more elaborate way for the construction (with or without the aid of centerings) of vaults and domes. These techniques, even today, are mostly practiced through self-constructive processes involving entire communities. All these traditional processes have undergone various technical refinements in the 20th century intended to further increase their effectiveness and reliability. In some cases they have been industrialized.

In recent decades, interest in raw earth has been revived due to its ecological sustainability and thermal and aesthetic properties. The advent of Additive Manufacturing (AM), or 3D printing, has opened new perspectives to bring raw earth construction into a new era of technical innovation.

MA is a digital fabrication process through an object is made by generating and adding successive layers of material. AM for the construction industry, which is called 3D Construction Printing (3DCP) has been developing since the early 2000s. Specifically, Liquid Deposition Modeling (LDM) technology allows viscous materials, including raw earth, to be deposited, de facto digitalizing a wet laying of the material. This technology has revolutionized the construction industry by offering a wide range of benefits, including reduced material waste, design flexibility, the ability to fabricate complex components, increased safety on the worksite, and reduced overall project costs by making construction more accessible and affordable, especially in areas where resources are limited or where there is a high demand for housing.

The aspect in which AM is linked to earthen construction processes which is emphasized in this text is its declination as a self-construction technology. Large-scale 3D printing in architecture as a self-building technique represents a significant breakthrough in the construction industry, offering an innovative and sustainable approach to the construction of housing and infrastructures. This methodology combines the potential of 3D printing with the capacity for self-construction, enabling individuals and communities to actively participate in the process of building their own homes. It also encourages innovation and exchange of knowledge and skills within communities, helping to preserve and promote local building traditions.

However, there are still challenges to be faced before AM can be fully adopted in the earthen construction industry. These include challenges developing materials suitable for 3D printing that are robust, durable, and environmentally friendly, as well as standardizing manufacturing processes and certifying the quality of printed components.

In conclusion, large-scale 3D printing in architecture as a self-building technique represents a unique opportunity to revolutionize the building industry through a massive re-input of raw earth material into

construction processes. AM meant in this way, with the use of raw earth material, would be beneficial for those populations that use this material in their construction processes due to economic reasons. However, those populations consider this material as an obstacle to their social aspirations as it is not aligned with modern progress.

At the same time, it would boost the use of raw earth by those people who are able to appreciate the earth for its qualities of ecological comfort. However, the same people are not able to use this material since it is outside standardized processes. With further technological developments and continued commitment from governments, institutions and communities, this innovative methodology could radically transform the way we design, build and inhabit the spaces of the future.

Keywords: Raw earth, Additive Manufacturing, self-made construction.